

Biomimetic Synthesis of Nitraria Alkaloids, based on Tetrahydropyridine Synthons

M J WANNER and G J KOOMEN*

Amsterdam Institute of Molecular Studies, Laboratory of Organic Chemistry, University of Amsterdam, Nieuwe Achtergracht 129, 1018 WS Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Manuscript received 8 September 1997

Many of the alkaloids found in Nitraria and Lupine species can be envisaged to arise from two simple building blocks, namely, tryptamine and tetrahydropyridine. In particular in the Nitraria species, the alkaloids occur as racemates in some cases, despite the presence of many stereocenters. We assume that racemic alkaloids might be formed without interference of enzymes via spontaneous reactions of highly reactive intermediates. By carrying out a biomimetic approach many of these alkaloids were obtained by us via chemical synthesis, based on this concept of reactive precursors. The paper discusses the preparation of racemic lupinine, spartein, and nitramine from tryptamine and the trimer of tetrahydropyridine, based on imine-enamine chemistry.

A variety of alkaloids, like nitramin (1), nitrarine (2), nazlinin (3), and nitramine (4) (Scheme 1) have been isolated from different species of the Nitraria family¹. An interesting feature of these alkaloids is the fact that they are isolated as racemates, even in cases where the molecule contains five or six stereocenters². This has been observed before for alkaloids like akuammicine³, yuehchukene⁴, and lucidene⁵.

Although it is widely accepted, that plant enzymes play a role in the biosynthetic steps in the plants⁶, it has been suggested before that in some cases a nonenzymic pathway cannot be excluded^{3,5}. Also, in the evolution of plants, nature has been carrying out one experiment after another to evolve an efficient defense mechanism. Many of the poisonous alkaloids found in plants today have helped these species to survive during thousands of centuries in a hostile environment by protecting them against animal consumption. This would imply that at a certain point in the evolution of the plant, more or less by coincidence, very

reactive molecules are formed, which give rise to the spontaneous uncatalyzed formation of complex alkaloid skeletons as racemates. In later stages, the plant might selectively convert one of the antipodes into chiral products or enzymatically destroy an antipode. Viewed in this way, the presence of racemic alkaloids in plants would be an indication, that these plants are in relatively early stages of their development. In terms of evolution this implies that the end-products of today ultimately might be used as the intermediates for future alkaloids.

The purpose of our research is to show that once the correct reactive biosynthetic precursors are prepared, the spontaneous formation of the racemic alkaloids can also be achieved in the laboratory under more or less biological conditions. The success of this approach in the biomimetic synthesis of nitramine (1)⁷ and the indole alkaloids nitrarine (2)⁸ and nazlinin (3)⁹⁻¹¹ has been described elsewhere.

Synthesis of lupinine based on tetrahydroanabasine

Nature is capable of producing an immense variety of rather different products from a very small number of building blocks, like for instance acetyl-CoA. In the case of nitraria alkaloids like nitramine (1), one can envisage a biosynthesis via two units of tetrahydropyridine, which can be formed readily from lysine via decarboxylation and oxidative deamination. Tetrahydropyridine exists as an equilibrium mixture of an imine 6 and the corresponding enamine 7. Since these molecules are electrophilic and nucleophilic species respectively, several reactions can be expected and indeed occur leading to a dimer and different trimers, depending on pH. Molecules like 6, 7 or 8 once formed in nature from lysine, possess the reactivity which might lead to spontaneous formation of a variety of products.

In the laboratory synthesis, the starting material is α -tripiperidein (5) which can be decomposed in water at pH 7. As indicated in Scheme 2, formation of other trimers is possible.

Scheme 2

For the biosynthesis of nitraria and lupine alkaloids, tetrahydroanabasine (**8**) is an important starting material, showing the close relation between the two alkaloid skeletons. Opening one ring via **10** (Scheme 3) leads to the optically active lupine alkaloids¹², whereas retro-Michael reaction via **12** followed by oxidation and hydrolysis to **13** constitutes a simple route to the racemic spirocyclic nitraria alkaloids⁷.

Also in the lab, the synthesis of racemic lupinine and epi-lupinine could be carried out from tetrahydroanabasine (**8**). The ring opening as depicted in Scheme 4 was realized

the more stable epilupinine skeleton. Pure racemic lupinine **11** was obtained via ozonolysis of **16** at -50° followed by addition of NaBH_4 . Under a variety of more vigorous conditions a mixture of lupinine and epi-lupinine was obtained¹⁵.

Synthesis of spartein from the lupinin skeleton

Another alkaloid, present in Lupine species is the triperidine spartein **22**. Although, at first glance, the relation between spartein and lupinine is not obvious, is at-

Scheme 3

with methoxyamine, leading in 98% yield to **14**, in which the stereochemistry was preserved. Oxidation was carried out with the commercially available di-*t*-butylorthoquinone to **15** (45%)¹³.

This reaction is strongly related to those catalyzed by the copper containing amine oxidases, which use TPQ as the cofactor¹⁴.

Under basic conditions, **15** is converted into the corresponding enamine, which could be reduced to **16** (89%). The hydrolysis of the oxime requires very mild conditions to avoid epimerization of the intermediate aldehyde **17** to

tractive to envisage that the biosynthesis of spartein only requires addition of one extra tetrahydropyridine moiety to the lupinine (or tetrahydroanabasine) skeleton. The question is, whether this process can be mimicked non-enzymic in the laboratory. Thus we carried out the reaction between enamine **8** and tetrahydropyridine (Scheme 5).

When in this case the oxime was split under very mild conditions with ozone¹⁶, imine/enamine equilibria are established in the aldehyde **20** under buffered acidic reaction conditions (NaOAc/HOAc). The diastereomer in which both substituents occupy axial positions can cyclize to **21**. With-

Scheme 4

out isolation, the cyclization product was converted with NaCNBH_3 into racemic sparteine (21%). When the oxime 19 was split under reductive conditions with TiCl_3/HCl at elevated temperatures, reduction with NaCNBH_3 resulted in the formation of 1:1 mixture of sparteine and β -isoparteine.

stable synthons in order to obtain the reactive bioprecursor 28 in a more efficient way. We assume however, that in the plant, where more time is available and lower yields are acceptable, the imine/enamine route is followed. In this case we utilized N-Boc piperidone as an intermediate¹⁷, since

Scheme 5

Synthesis of nitramine via piperidone units

The formation of the more complex alkaloid nitramine (4), despite its six stereocenters present in *Nitraria schoberi* as a racemate, can be envisaged from the highly symmetrical intermediate 28 (C_{2v} symmetry), containing two conjugated imine functions with several possibilities of forming imine/enamine equilibria (Scheme 7).

Although in principle, synthesis of 28 could be realized via imine/enamine chemistry, we preferred to utilize more

in the case of nitramine, this had proven to be a very useful synthon. Reactions of glutaraldehyde and tetrahydropyridine gave rise to very complicated mixtures which were not of practical value for a laboratory synthesis. So, protected glutaraldehyde derivative 24 was condensed with the lithium enolate of 23 (Scheme 6)¹⁸.

Without isolation, the condensation product was converted into 25 via mesylation and elimination. After hydrolysis of the acetal function, a second condensation with

the lithium enolate of 23 was carried out. In 26 the complete carbon framework for the spontaneous cyclization has been constructed; it only requires adjustment of the oxidation state. Lithium triethylborohydride proved to be effective

for this reduction, leading to a mixture of the unstable precursors 27¹⁹. As indicated in Scheme 7, in the alcohol 30 cyclization can be easily envisaged if one of the dihydropyridine rings and the OH group both occupy axial positions. Especially in this case, where nitramine was synthe-

When 28 was heated with aqueous phosphate buffer at pH 7, the expected three successive cyclizations took place, giving rise to the formation of nitramine in approximately

20% yield. As indicated in Scheme 7, in the alcohol 30 cyclization can be easily envisaged if one of the dihydropyridine rings and the OH group both occupy axial positions. Especially in this case, where nitramine was synthesized for the first time, the biomimetic approach based on hypothetical biosynthetic schemes has clearly proven its usefulness. Application of this approach to the synthesis of Manzamine derivatives and other complex alkaloids is currently underway.

References

1. Z. OSMANOV, A. A. IBRAGIMOV, and S. YU. YUSUNOV, *Khim. Prir. Soedin.*, 1982, 75, 126, 400; *Chem. Nat. Compd.*, 1982, 18, 70, 121, 372; A. A. IBRAGIMOV and S. YU. YUSUNOV, *Khim. Prir. Soedin.*, 1986, 730; 1988, 82; *Chem. Nat. Compd.*, 1986, 22, 680; 1988, 24, 71.
2. See 1, and B. TASHKODZHAEV, A. A. IBRAGIMOV, B. T.

- IBRAGIMOV, and S. YU. YUNUSOV, *Khim. Prir. Soedin.*, 1989, 30; *Chem. Nat. Compd.*, 1989, 25, 24; S.-M. NASIROV, A. A. IBRAGIMOV, V. G. ANDRIANOV, S. KH. MAEKH, YU. T. STRUCHKOV, and S. YU. YUNUSOV, *Khim. Prir. Soedin.*, 1976, 334; *Chem. Nat. Compd.*, 1976, 12, 294.
3. P. N. EDWARDS and G. F. SMITH, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 215.
 4. Y-CH KONG, K-F CHENG, R. C. CAMBIE, and P. G. WATERMAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1985, 47.
 5. H. WEENEN, M. H. H. NKUNYA, A. ABDUL EL-FADL, S. HARKEMA, and B. ZWANENBURG., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1990, 55, 5107.
 6. D. R. DALTON in "Studies in Organic Chemistry", ed. P. G. GASSMAN, M. Dekker, 1979, Vol. 7, p. 4.
 7. M. J. WANNER and G. J. KOOMEN in "Advances in Natural Products Chemistry", ed. ATTA-UR RAHMAN, Harwood, 1992, p. 203; M. J. WANNER and G. J. KOOMEN, "Studies in Natural Product Chemistry", ed. ATTA-UR RAHMAN, Elsevier, New York, 1993, Vol. 14, p. 731.
 8. M. J. WANNER and G. J. KOOMEN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1994, 59, 7479.
 9. L. ÜSTÜNES, A. ÖZER, G. M. LAEKEMAN, J. CORTHOUT, L. A. C. PIETERS, W. BAETEN, A. G. HERMAN, M. CLAEYS, and A. J. VLIETINCK, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1991, 54, 959.
 10. M. J. WANNER, A. J. VELZEL, and G. J. KOOMEN, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1993, 174.
 11. S. MAHBOOBI, W. WAGNER, TH. BURGEMEISTER, and W. WIEGREBE, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1994, 327, 563; S. MAHBOOBI, W. WAGNER, and TH. BURGEMEISTER, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1995, 328, 371.
 12. W. M. GOLEBIEWSKI and I. D. SPENSER, *Can J. Chem.*, 1985, 63, 2707.
 13. E. J. COREY and K. J. ACHIWA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 91, 1429; E. CHENG, J. BOTZEM, M. J. WANNER, B. E. A. BURM, and G. J. KOOMEN, *Tetrahedron*, 1996, 52, 6725.
 14. S. M. JANES, M. M. PALCIC, C. H. SCAMAN, A. J. SMITH, D. E. BROWN, D. M. DOOLEY, M. MURE, and J. P. KLINMAN, *Biochemistry*, 1992, 31, 12147; D. M. DOOLEY, M. A. MCGUIRL, D. E. BROWN, P. N. TUROWSKI, W. S. MCINTIRE, and P. F. KNOWLES, *Nature*, 1991, 349, 262.
 15. M. J. WANNER and G. J. KOOMEN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1996, 61, 5581.
 16. K. GRIESBAUM, B. OVEZ, T. SUNG HUH, and Y. DONG, *Liebigs Ann.*, 1995, 1571.
 17. D. L. FLYNN, R. E. ZELLE, and P. A. GRIECO, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, 48, 2424.
 18. M. J. WANNER and G. J. KOOMEN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1995, 60, 5634.
 19. M. J. FISHER and L. E. OVERMAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1990, 55, 1447.